

COMPARISON OF EFFICACY BETWEEN INTRAVENOUS KETOROLAC VERSUS INTRAVENOUS IBUPROFEN FOR POST-OPERATIVE PAIN RELIEF IN PACU PATIENTS UNDERGOING KNEE SURGERIES

Najam Ul Hassan^{*1}, Ambar Fayyaz Jafri², Syed Ali Mazhar Rizvi³,
Shujaat Hussain⁴, Hassam Abdullah⁵, Junaid Zafar⁶

^{1,2,3,4,5,6}CMH Rwp. Anesthesia Dept

¹jafry806@gmail.com, ²ambar.fayyaz@gmail.com, ³dralirizvi@yahoo.com,
⁴shujaat169@gmail.com, ⁵hassam986@gmail.com, ⁶junaidzafaramc@hotmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21159722>

Keywords

Anesthesia, arthroscopy, ibuprofen, ketorolac, knee, pain, post-operative

Article History

Received: 25 April 2024
Accepted: 07 June 2024
Published: 22 June 2024

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Najam Ul Hassan

Abstract

Objective: To compare the efficacy of pain relief and adverse effects profile when comparing intravenous ketorolac versus intravenous ibuprofen for post-procedure pain relief in post-anesthesia care unit (PACU) in patients undergoing knee arthroscopy

Study Design: Randomized controlled trial

Place and Duration of Study: Department of Anesthesia, Combined Military Hospital, Rawalpindi from Jun 2023-Dec 2023.

Methodology: Group I received IV Ibuprofen at a dose of 800 mg at the following interval 2 hours before procedure and 30 minutes after the procedure in the recovery. Group K received IV Ketorolac 30 mg at the same time intervals before and after the procedure. Primary variables studied were median pain scores assessed on a standard 10-point visual analog scale. Pain scores were checked in both groups pre-operatively, and at 1- 3- and 6- hours post-procedure.

Results: Median pain scores pre-procedure were 6.00 (0.00) versus 6.00 (1.00) between both groups ($p=0.339$). Median pain scores at 1 hr post-op were 2.00 (1.00) versus 3.00 (1.00) between both groups ($p<0.001$). Same score assessed at 3 hr post-op were 2.00 (1.00) versus 3.00 (0.00) ($p<0.001$) and at 6 hr post-op were 2.00 (1.00) versus 4.00 (1.00) ($p<0.001$). Mean total dose of rescue analgesia used while in recovery was 4.33 ± 0.50 mg in Group I versus 8.39 ± 0.59 in Group K ($p<0.001$).

Conclusion: We conclude that IV Ibuprofen provides better analgesia, reduced opioid consumption and a better adverse effects profile in patients undergoing knee arthroscopy.

INTRODUCTION

Patient care in the post-anesthesia care unit remains an important priority for the anesthetist¹. It is reported that approximately 50% of all anesthesia complications occur in the immediate post-operative time and early vigilance and prompt intervention can prevent patient morbidity and

mortality^{2, 3}. The most common complications seen in the PACU include pain, hypoxia, nausea, vomiting, bronchospasm⁴. The main cause for these complications is related to the type of surgery, intra-operative time and most importantly the type and doses of drugs used per-operatively

and in the post-operative period⁵. The residual effects anesthesia require that the patient be monitored and shifted once pre-requisite criteria are met including consciousness, threshold for pain and voiding.

Patients presenting with adverse effects in the PACU may require admission for further monitoring⁶. Procedures done as day care anesthesia cases are planned so that the patient can be sent back home the same day after complete recovery⁷. Any drugs or interventions used during surgery that may hamper or delay recovery result in hospital admissions causing unnecessary resource constraint and burden in medical setups⁸. It is recommended that doses of opioids and sedative agents titrated in a way that the patient can fully recover in the PACU and can be discharged safely post-procedure.

The major complain after orthopedics arthroscopies is pain in the immediate post-operative period⁹. The procedure is mainly done as a day care procedure worldwide and use of drugs for pain post-operatively require that the choice of drugs selected should have minimal residual effects for early recovery. The use of opioids is generally not preferable in standard doses but combined with other non-opioids as a multimodal regime to decrease their untoward effects and decreasing their dose in this scenario of pain relief with minimal adverse effects need to be investigated for their efficacy and profile¹⁰. Both ketorolac and ibuprofen belong to the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) category with minimal effects on consciousness. There is no study in our local demographic area comparing both drugs in the PACU for pain relief after arthroscopy. Our study aims to see which drug is more suitable for effective pain relief in patients presenting for elective arthroscopies as day care procedures.

METHODOLOGY:

This randomized controlled trial was carried out at the Department of Anesthesia, Combined Military Hospital Rawalpindi from Jun 2023-Dec 2023 after approval from the ethical review board vide letter no. The sample size for two groups was calculated keeping the confidence interval at

95%, power of test at 80% with time to first dose of opioid rescue analgesia in the ibuprofen and ketorolac group being 77.62 ± 33.03 minutes and 55.78 ± 35.37 minutes respectively with a mean difference of 21.84 ± 2.34 minutes¹¹. Minimum sample size according to the WHO calculator came out to be 33 for each group. We included 70 patients in each group in the final study protocol after assessment through non-probability consecutive sampling via lottery method according to the inclusion criteria furnished keeping in line with CONSORT guidelines. (Figure-1).

Inclusion criteria included all patients >18 years and <60 years presenting for knee arthroscopy under general anesthesia to the orthopedic department and referred to the pre-anesthesia clinic for assessment.

Exclusion criteria included patients < 18 years and > 60 years, pregnancy, patients with known allergies to NSAIDs and opioids, patients already on NSAID therapy in the last 2 weeks, patients with anemia, dyspepsia, history of gastric bleed, advanced cardiac or respiratory disease, patients undergoing procedure in spinal anesthesia and patients unwilling to be included in the study.

The study method included all patients as per the inclusion criteria furnished. The patients were randomized into two groups of 70 patients each. Group I (n=70) to receive IV Ibuprofen and Group K (n=70) to receive IV Ketorolac. The patients were initially counseled in detail about the study protocol and a written informed consent was taken before enrolment in the study protocol. This was a single center, double blinded, parallel randomized controlled trial and only the pharmacist in the operation theater medical store was unblinded to the treatment regime being given in both groups. The randomization to the allocated groups was done on presentation in the pre-operative detention room with sealed envelopes by a resident anesthetist unaware of the study protocol. The pharmacist prepared the treatment regime in sealed burettes marked X and Y to be given to the consultant in the operating room before during and after the procedure. Group I received IV Ibuprofen at a dose of 800 mg at the following interval 2 hours before procedure

and 30 minutes after the procedure in the recovery. Group K received IV Ketorolac 30 mg at the same time intervals before and after the procedure. General anesthesia was administered in both groups with IV Propofol 2 mg/kg, IV Nalbuphine 0.15 mg/kg and maintained with Isoflurane 1.0 MAC (minimum alveolar concentration). Pre-operative antiemetic medication included IV Dexamethasone 4 mg and IV Ondansetron 8 mg stat. Appropriately sized i-gel (laryngeal mask airway) was used to secure the airway in both groups. Patients were extubated and shifted to the recovery.

Primary variables studied were median pain scores assessed on a standard 10-point visual analog scale. Pain scores were checked in both groups pre-operatively, and at 1- 3- and 6- hours post-procedure. Rescue analgesia was given in the form of IV Nalbuphine (opioid) once the pain on the

standard 10 point VAS (Visual Analog Scale)¹² reached 5 on the scale despite treatment given on both groups. Time for first dose of rescue analgesia and total dose used were calculated. Adverse effects in both groups were assessed during detention in the recovery. Patients requiring higher doses of opioids and requiring subsequent admissions for monitoring were also noted.

Demographic data were statistically described in terms of mean and SD, frequencies, and percentages when appropriate. Independent samples t-test was used to compare statistically significant means. Median values were compared using the Mann-Whitney U test. Chi-square test was used to compare frequency variables. A p value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All statistical calculations were performed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences 26.0

Figure-I: Phases Of The Randomized Controlled Trial

RESULTS:

A total of 140 patients were analyzed in the final study protocol randomized into Group I (n=70) and Group K (n=70). Mean age of patients in Group I was 37.13±7.74 years versus 36.69±7.72 years in Group K (p=0.735). Mean weight was 74.03±4.41 kg in Group I versus 74.44±4.35 kg in Group K (p=0.577). Gender distribution revealed 57 (81.4%) males and 13 (18.6%) females in Group I versus 58 (82.9%) males and 12 (17.1%) females in Group K (p=0.825). Mean duration of surgery between both groups was 38.50±5.24 minutes in Group I versus 38.74±5.31 minutes in Group K (p=0.786) (Table-I).

Comparison between primary variables showed that median pain scores pre-procedure were 6.00 (0.00) versus 6.00 (1.00) between both groups

(p=0.339). Median pain scores at 1 hr post-op were 2.00 (1.00) versus 3.00 (1.00) between both groups (p<0.001). Same score assessed at 3 hr post-op were 2.00 (1.00) versus 3.00 (0.00) (p<0.001) and at 6 hr post-op were 2.00 (1.00) versus 4.00 (1.00) (p<0.001). Mean total dose of rescue analgesia used while in recovery was 4.33±0.50 mg in Group I versus 8.39±0.59 in Group K (p<0.001). Patients who required re-admission for monitoring were 02 (2.9%) patients in Group I versus 09 (12.9%) patients in Group K (p=0.028) (Table-II).

When comparing the adverse effects profile, nausea was reported in 07 (10%) patients versus 09 (12.9%) patients between both groups (p=0.595). The incidence of vomiting was 03 (4.3%) patients in Group I versus 12 (17.1%) patients in Group K (p=0.014). Dizziness was

reported by 02 (2.9%) patients in Group I versus 07 (10%) patients in Group K (p=0.085) (Table-III).

TABLES

TABLE-I DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS BETWEEN BOTH GROUPS (n=140)

VARIABLE	GROUP I (n=70)	GROUP K (n=70)	p VALUE
MEAN AGE (YEARS)	37.13±7.74	36.69±7.72	0.735
MEAN WEIGHT (KG)	74.03±4.41	74.44±4.35	0.577
GENDER			
• MALE	57 (81.4%)	58 (82.9%)	0.825
• FEMALE	13 (18.6%)	12 (17.1%)	
MEAN DURATION OF SURGERY (MINUTES)	38.50±5.24	38.74±5.31	0.786

TABLE-II COMPARISON OF PRIMARY VARIABLES (n=140)

VARIABLE	GROUP I (n=70)	GROUP K (n=70)	p VALUE
MEDIAN PAIN SCORES PRE-PROCEDURE	6.00 (0.00)	6.00 (1.00)	0.339
MEDIAN PAIN SCORES AT 1 HOUR POST-OP	2.00 (1.00)	3.00 (1.00)	<0.001
MEDIAN PAIN SCORE AT 3 HOURS POST-OP	2.00 (1.00)	3.00 (0.00)	<0.001
MEDIAN PAIN SCORES AT 6 HOURS POST-OP	2.00 (1.00)	4.00 (1.00)	<0.001
MEAN TIME TO FIRST DOSE OF RESCUE ANALGESIA (MIN)	115.33±2.87	69.29±5.44	<0.001
MEAN TOTAL DOSE OF RESCUE ANALGESIA USED (MG)	4.33±0.50	8.39±0.59	<0.001
REQUIRED ADMISSION FOR MONITORING	02 (2.9%)	09 (12.9%)	0.028

TABLE-III ADVERSE EFFECTS PROFILE (n=140)

VARIABLE	GROUP I (n=70)	GROUP K (n=70)	p VALUE
NAUSEA	07 (10%)	09 (12.9%)	0.595
VOMITING	03 (4.3%)	12 (17.1%)	0.014
DIZZINESS	02 (2.9%)	07 (10%)	0.085

DISCUSSION:

The rationale behind conducting this study in our demographic setup was multi-factorial. We aimed to reduce the use of opioids in day care procedures to prevent the untoward side effects like headache dizziness, nausea, and vomiting. Since pain is subjective for each patient¹³, the need for opioid rescue doses may not be completely removed but their dose can be reduced by a multi-modal

analgesia regime which would decrease the incidence and frequency of associated side-effects¹⁴. Median pain scores as assessed post-arthroscopy for the knee are between the moderate to severe pain ranges¹⁵. This requires good analgesia if the patient is to be discharged on the same day as a day care case. The burden of patients in our setups requires good and optimized patient turnover to prevent backlog of surgeries and

effectively manage patients in time for a complication free discharge.

The major demographic population in our study presenting for surgery was in their mid-thirties to late forties and majority of the cases had a history of trauma during exercise, exertion, or road-traffic accidents. The primary variable for median pain scores studied showed that median pain scores in both groups were statistically comparable before the procedure. There was a consistently constant value for median pain scores in the ibuprofen group when compared with the ketorolac group which showed increasing pain scores from the first to the sixth hour in the recovery. Studies done by Paul et al⁹ and King et al¹⁶ showed nearly similar results. Studies done by showed that median pain scores were comparable between both groups at the 6 hour interval. But our study found a statistically significant difference in the pain scores that were tabulated with a better pain profile seen in the ibuprofen group.

When talking about the time and the dose of rescue analgesia required in both groups, we found that the consumption of opioid was halved in the ibuprofen group when compared with the ketorolac group with minimal side effects at the total dose consumed in the group. Similarly, time to request additional doses of analgesics in the ibuprofen group was doubled to 2 hours as compared to one in the ketorolac group. These results are in line with studies carried out by Gazendum et al¹⁵ and Foster et al¹⁷ which showed reduced consumption and increase pain free times post-procedure in patients.

Local studies done by Zubair et al¹⁸ also showed that ibuprofen as a better analgesic for day care surgeries reducing the pain scores, time to analgesia requirement and a better adverse effects profile. They compared their results in inguinal hernia surgeries and found similar results. The incidence of nausea and vomiting was more in the ketorolac group, but it was related to the increased dose of the opioids used that by ketorolac itself. Ibuprofen at a dose of 800 mg provided a better adverse effects profile and early discharge for patients.

RECOMMEDATIONS:

The study recommends the use ibuprofen as an excellent addition to the multi-modal analgesia regime for patients undergoing day-care knee arthroscopy.

CONCLUSION:

We conclude that IV Ibuprofen provides better analgesia, reduced opioid consumption and a better adverse effects profile in patients undergoing knee arthroscopy.

LIMITATIONS:

The limitations are that the study is single center only.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

None.

REFERENCES

1. Wang X-l, He M, Feng Y. Handover Patterns in the PACU: A Review of the Literature. *Journal of PeriAnesthesia Nursing*. 2021;36(2):136-41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jopan.2020.05.005>
2. Dias TLF, Anjos C, Andrade J, Funez MI. Analysis of perioperative variables and their relationship with complications in the Post-Anesthetic Care Unit. *Rev Enferm UFSM*. 2022;12:e42.
3. ŞAHİN SK, ŞELİMEN HD. Evaluation of Complication Development in General Surgery Patients Admitted to the Post Anesthesia Care Unit. *Clinical and Experimental Health Sciences*. 2022;12(2):383-9. <https://doi.org/10.33808/clinexphealthsci.892276>
4. Kula Sahin S, Selimen HD. Evaluation of complication development in general surgery patients admitted to the post anesthesia care unit. 2022. <https://doi.org/10.33808/clinexphealthsci.892276>

5. Kearney D, Smith C. Opioid Use and Extended Stays in the Post Anesthesia Care Unit (PACU). *Journal of PeriAnesthesia Nursing*. 2021;36(4):e22-e3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jopan.2021.06.068>
6. Santa Cruz Mercado LA, Liu R, Bharadwaj KM, Johnson JJ, Gutierrez R, Das P, et al. Association of intraoperative opioid administration with postoperative pain and opioid use. *JAMA Surgery*. 2023;158(8). DOI:10.1001/jamasurg.2023.2009
7. Tang R, Santosa KB, Vu JV, Lin LA, Lai Y-L, Englesbe MJ, et al. Preoperative opioid use and readmissions following surgery. *Annals of surgery*. 2022;275(1):e99-e106. <https://doi.org/10.1097/SLA.00000000000003827>
8. Urman RD, Seger DL, Fiskio JM, Neville BA, Harry EM, Weiner SG, et al. The burden of opioid-related adverse drug events on hospitalized previously opioid-free surgical patients. *Journal of Patient Safety*. 2021;17(2):e76-e83. DOI: [10.1097/PTS.0000000000000566](https://doi.org/10.1097/PTS.0000000000000566)
9. Paul RW, Szukics PF, Brutico J, Tjoumakaris FP, Freedman KB. Postoperative multimodal pain management and opioid consumption in arthroscopy clinical trials: a systematic review. *Arthroscopy, sports medicine, and rehabilitation*. 2022;4(2):e721-e46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asmr.2021.09.011>
10. Karpetas GZ, Spyraiki MK, Giakoumakis SI, Fligou FG, Megas PD, Voyagis GS, et al. Multimodal analgesia protocol for pain management after total knee arthroplasty: comparison of three different regional analgesic techniques. *Journal of Musculoskeletal & Neuronal Interactions*. 2021;21(1):104.
11. Uribe AA, Arbona FL, Flanigan DC, Kaeding CC, Palettas M, Bergese SD. Comparing the efficacy of IV ibuprofen and ketorolac in the management of postoperative pain following arthroscopic knee surgery. A randomized double-blind active comparator pilot study. *Frontiers in surgery*. 2018;5:59. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsurg.2018.00059>
12. Bodian CA, Freedman G, Hossain S, Eisenkraft JB, Beilin Y. The visual analog scale for pain: clinical significance in postoperative patients. *The Journal of the American Society of Anesthesiologists*. 2001;95(6):1356-61. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00000542-200112000-00013>
13. Pouromran F, Radhakrishnan S, Kamarthi S. Exploration of physiological sensors, features, and machine learning models for pain intensity estimation. *Plos one*. 2021;16(7):e0254108. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0254108>
14. Thijssen M, Timmerman L, Koning NJ, Rinia M, van Dijk JF, Cheuk-Alam J, et al. Multimodal analgesia practices for knee and hip arthroplasties in the Netherlands. A prospective observational study from the PAIN OUT registry. *Plos one*. 2022;17(12):e0279606. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0279606>
15. Gazendam A, Ekhtiari S, Horner NS, Nucci N, Dookie J, Ayeni OR. Perioperative nonopioid analgesia reduces postoperative opioid consumption in knee arthroscopy: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Knee Surgery, Sports Traumatology, Arthroscopy*. 2021;29:1887-903. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00167-020-06256-2>

16. King JL, Richey B, Yang D, Olsen E, Muscatelli S, Hake ME. Ketorolac and bone healing: a review of the basic science and clinical literature. *European Journal of Orthopaedic Surgery & Traumatology*. 2023;1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00590-023-03715-7>
17. Foster JA, Kavolus MW, Landy DC, Pectol RW, Sneed CR, Kinchelow DL, et al. Low-Dose Short-Term Scheduled Ketorolac Reduces Opioid Use and Pain in Orthopaedic Polytrauma Patients: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *Journal of Orthopaedic Trauma*. 2022;10.1097.
18. Zubair R, Mirza MR, Channa MA, Yaqoob U. Comparing the effects of Ketorolac and Ibuprofen on postoperative pain relief after para umbilical hernia repair. A randomized clinical trial. *Pakistan Journal of Surgery*. 2022;38(1).

